

Mechanical pulping for manufacture of hand made paper from Date-Palm leaves (*Phoenix dactylifera* – L)

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Manuscript received 4 June 2009, revised 18 November 2009, accepted 26 November 2009

Abstract : The present paper highlights the production of pulp from agro-residues by mechanical pulping for the benefit of Indian paper industry. Date-Palm leaf (DPL), a renewable agro-residue is an excellent raw material for making pulp and paper of different grades due to high alpha cellulose (50–58%) and hemi cellulose contents (26–32%). These constituents play a stellar role in mechanical pulping i.e. in beating operation without using any chemical. Ultimate fibre length (1.25 mm to 2.50 mm) is also higher than fibres of other agro-residues, recycled cotton rag and paper. Yield and mechanical properties of the pulp of 100% DPL fibre obtained by mechanical pulping process attained higher values as compared to its blends with recycled cotton rag. Chemo-mechanical process is costly and not environment friendly. Moreover, yield and mechanical properties of the paper obtained in this process are poor. Hemi cellulose (more than 25%) and non-cellulosic polysaccharide which exist in cell wall of fibres contribute to efficient beating operation and fibre bonding. Hemi cellulose also contributes largely towards higher burst index, tensile index and folding endurance to the pulp sheet specially produced without using any chemical in the entire process.

Keywords : Date-Palm leaf, hand made paper, mechanical pulping, properties.

Introduction

Paper is a thin, flat material produced by the compression of fibres. The fibres used are usually natural contain cellulose. The conventional cellulosic materials for making pulp and paper throughout the world are wood pulp, pulpwood trees (largely soft woods) and bamboos, but these are available only in limited quantities in the global market and presently there is a gradual depletion of this source. Hence, intensive efforts need to be made to look for an alternate source like non-wood fibres¹.

India has a diversified and abundant source of rich non-wood fibre⁴ as shown in Table 1. But the chemical composition of these fibrous materials as shown in

Table 2 reveals that DPL has maximum contents of α -cellulose and hemi-cellulose⁵. Moreover, the ultimate fibre length, breadth and L/B are very high for making good quality paper for different end uses as shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Chemical composition of some agro-residues in per cent

Agro-residue	α -Cellulose	Hemi cellulose	Lignin	Ash
Bagasse	39.0	32.0	20.0	3.3
Rice straw	26.0	30.0	22.0	14.4
Wheat straw	29.5	28.0	20.0	14.8
Jute stick	41.0	34.0	23.0	0.8
Date-Palm leaf	55.0	31.0	14.0	1.8

Table 1. Annual potential of agro-residues based fibres in India

Agro-residues	Availability (Million tonnes)
Wheat straw	22
Rice straw	15
Bagasse	12
Jute, Mesta, Kenaf	2
Date-Palm leaves	5

The traditional methods of manufacturing pulp and paper in the world are chemical, chemo-mechanical, bio-mechanical and mechanical methods. But no method has yet been standardized to manufacture pulp and paper from Date-Palm leaves. Hence, the present exercise is to try out mechanical pulping of DPL so as to economise the pulping process and make it environment friendly so that high pulp yield and excellent physico-mechanical properties of paper can be attained.

Table 3. Physical properties of ultimate cell of different agro-residues

Ultimate cell	DPL fibre	Jute stick	Bagasse	Rice straw	Wheat straw	Recycled cotton	Waste paper
Length (L) mm	1.25-2.50	0.7-0.9	0.9-1.25	0.5-0.7	0.6-0.9	0.6-0.8	0.2-0.4
Breadth (B) $\times 10^{-3}$ mm	8-16	4-12	7-9	5-7	5-7	5-6	3-5
L/B ratio	150-190	100-120	125-138	100-116	120-128	120-133	66-80

Experimental

Air dried Date-Palm leaves were chopped to 1-1.5 cm in length and immersed in water at room temperature overnight for 24 h to make the leaves soft and clean so that a portion of pectin, dirt and other foreign materials can be removed prior to beating operation to reduce the energy consumption unlike thermo-mechanical (TM) pulping from logs. Water was poured in the beater machine (electrically driven) till half of the cemented tank (oval shape) is filled with water. The ratio of liquid : raw material was maintained at 1 : 10 (w/v). The small chips float partly and partly immersed in water around the beater when the beating treatment proceeds. Pulping takes place due to the mechanical action of the rotating fine-toothed saw located between the base plate and the arms of the beater.

The pulp slurry (after two hours of beating treatment) was further diluted to a very thin slurry and converted to paper sheets by standard process. Natural drying of the sheets was allowed to take place and finally, trimming and calendaring of the paper sheet was made to make it glossy and uniformly textured. Handmade paper was also made from blends of Date-Palm leaf (DPL) and recycled cotton rags (RCR) in different proportions. The physico-mechanical properties e.g. yield of pulp, area density, burst index, tensile index and fold endurance of paper sheets were determined.

Results and discussion

The observations showed that pulp yield % and mechanical strength parameters of paper made from Date-Palm leaves (DPL) exhibited highest values. It is a fact that mechanical hydration of fibre takes place during beating process, in which foreign materials inside the chips and lignin in leaf cells are broken and are partially removed. Since lignin cannot be fully removed from pulp,

pulp yield was relatively higher, about 90-95% due to higher content of α -cellulose and lesser content of lignin⁷.

Moreover, hemi cellulose plays the key role for making good quality paper of acceptable physico-chemical properties without using any chemicals. When the beating treatment proceeds, the internal film structure is loosened and the fibres swell rapidly to about twice the original diameter. Swollen hemi cellulose on the surface of the fibres takes an active part in the formation of bonds between the fibres in the paper sheet. It precisely acts as glue. The more surface material is swollen and dissolved in water, the stronger is the surface tension and larger will be the areas of contact between fibres leading to formation of a strong and even surfaced sheet⁸. As compared to other agro-wastes, Date-Palm leaf (DPL) has higher fibre length, higher L/B ratio, higher α -cellulose, higher hemi cellulose and lower lignin thus contributing to the ideal conditions for getting much better quality paper than others.

When Date-Palm leaf (DPL) fibre pulp was blended with recycled cotton rag (RCR) pulp of shorter length as raw material for paper production, the pulp yield increased with increase in content of RCR, but strength properties decreased (Table 4). This is due to the fact that α -cellulose content (about 70%) is higher in recycled cotton rag (RCR) than in Date-Palm leaf (58%) contributing to higher pulp yield. But the ultimate fibre length of DPL fibre (1.25-2.50 mm) is much higher than RCR (0.8-1.0 mm) resulting in higher strength properties of paper. Moreover, the hemi cellulose content of DPL fibre (26-30%) that acts as a binding agent is much higher than that of RCR (about 2-5%) giving rise to greater values of fold endurance of paper. Hence, more the content of DPL in the feed, higher the strength and other parameters of the

Table 4. Physico-mechanical properties of hand made paper from Date-Palm leaves (DPL) alone or its blends with recycled cotton rag (RCR) by mechanical pulping process

Raw material ratio	Yield of pulp (%)	Basis weight (g/m ²)	Burst index (Kpa.m ² g)	Tested as IS: 1060	
				Tensile index (Nm/g)	Folding endurance (No)
DPL : RCR	80.60	120	1.69	15.8	15-21
100 : 0	83.80	326	3.586	21.5	35-40
	91.8	350	3.759	23.8	36-41
DPL : RCR	81.20	125	1.532	13.7	11-17
75 : 25	85.50	340	2.99	19.2	21-25
	89.00	361	2.879	20.8	26-30
DPL : RCR	82.30	136	1.216	10.9	10-18
50 : 50	86.70	352	2.111	16.6	19-23
	89.90	385	2.094	17.8	20-25
DPL : RCR	82.70	149	1.085	8.6	9-13
25 : 75	90.80	3393	1.953	12.8	15-20
	92.90	420	1.982	13.4	17-19
DPL : RCR	83.10	156	0.963	5.2	7-14
0 : 100	92.10	428	0.987	9.2	11-17
	94.20	447	1.032	4.1	11-18

hand made paper obtained from it. So, the results indicated that mechanical properties of different grades of paper made of 100% DPL pulp exhibited higher strength parameters and there is gradual decrease of strength with gradual reduction of the quantity of DPL in the pulp or increase of content of recycled cotton rags (RCR). However, considering the use of different grades of paper in different application areas, a suitable compromise is the optimum choice.

Conclusions :

Date-Palm leaf (DPL), the agri-residue and sustainable resource has proved itself to be most promising alternative for hardwood. Mechanical pulping is eco-friendly, cost effective and energy intensive, as there is no use of chemical and bleaching agent and the process does not involve any additional source of energy like thermal energy.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. S. K. Bhattacharyya, Director, Dr. A. K. Roy, Head, Division of Chemical and Bio-chemical Processing and Dr. M. Naskar, Sr.

Scientist, NIRJAFT, Kolkata for rendering support and assistance to carry out the work.

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